

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Analysis of factors that affect the performance of nurses in inpatient room type c hospitals in 2024

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Abstract

Background: The professionalism of nurses in providing nursing services can affect the results of nurse performance. If the performance of nurses in basic services is maximum, then the quality of health services will be better. The decline in performance results in patient and family satisfaction, which will have an impact on the quality of hospital services. One of the factors that affect the risk of declining performance is workload, working period, motivation and incentives. This study aims to analyze the influence of workload, work period, motivation and incentives on the performance of nurses in the Type C Hospital Inpatient Room in 2024.

Methods: The type of research used is observational analytical research using a cross sectional research design with univariate tests, bivariate and multivariate tests. The population in this study is all nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital with a sampling technique using a total sampling of 131 people. Data analysis uses chi-square test and logistic regression.

Results: The results showed that there was an effect of workload on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital ($0.001 < 0.05$), there was no effect of working period on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital ($0.312 > 0.05$), there was an effect between motivation on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital ($0.001 < 0.05$), and there was an effect between incentives on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital ($0.001 < 0.05$). The motivation variable was the most influential variable on performance with an Exp(B) result of 42,991.

Conclusion: Therefore, efforts to improve nurse performance must focus more on efforts to increase nurses' work motivation. In addition, workload reduction and incentive system evaluation also need to be carried out to support the improvement of nurse performance.

Keywords: Nurse Performance; Workload; Working Period; Motivation; Incentives

1. Introduction

Hospitals are one of the services industry that provide health services. As a service industry, hospitals must also carry out business functions in their managerial, one of which is how to produce a quality or quality service product. In the health service industry, service quality is very important in realizing customer satisfaction, especially since this is related to a person's life and death. In an increasingly competitive environment, hospitals must be increasingly aware of the need to provide the best quality of service for their customers (1).

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The main medical service in the hospital is inpatient service. This is because inpatient services are different from other medical services because they are a place of interaction between patients and parties in the hospital and last for a long time (Pradana, 2017). Efforts to maintain the quality of health services in hospitals are inseparable from the important role of the nursing profession. In the inpatient unit, nursing staff are at the forefront of health services with the first and longest contact with patients, namely for 24 hours per day and 7 days per week, so nurses hold key positions in the field of nursing services. Nursing services in hospitals are the largest producers of activities so that they reflect the quality of hospital services. Nurses in hospitals not only have an obligation to provide services to patients but also expect services from the hospital so that what they are entitled to can be well received (2).

Increasing and consolidating the role of nurses has recently become a demand of the community, both in health services in general because it is a paramedic profession and nursing in particular because it provides comprehensive health services. Nurse performance can be measured based on several indicators, including the quantity of work results, the quality of work products, efficiency in carrying out tasks, work discipline, initiative, precision, leadership, honesty and creativity. The demands and needs of quality nursing care in the future are challenges that must be prepared in a real way and handled in a fundamental, directed and earnest manner from the hospital. This can be achieved by the joint efforts of all parties to improve the quality of nurse education, develop nurse professionalism, and improve the quality of health services as a whole (3).

Nursing services are a determining factor in the success of health services in hospitals, because 80% of health services in the world are provided by nurses. This shows that nurses play a major role in almost every aspect of healthcare, from basic care to intensive care in the inpatient room. They are the health workers who interact most directly with patients, so the quality of health services is highly dependent on the competence and performance of nurses. Meanwhile, as many as 40% of health service providers in Indonesia are nursing staff. This percentage is quite large and reflects that nurses are the largest group of healthcare professionals in the country. With this significant number, nurses have an important role in providing quality health services, both in hospitals and other health facilities. Nursing staff make a considerable contribution to the services provided by a hospital, because nursing services provide constant and continuous service with customers, namely patients and their families for 24 hours a day and 7 days a week. Therefore, the service of nursing staff determines the quality and shapes the image of the hospital (3). Nursing as a form of professional service is an integral part that cannot be separated from the overall health service effort. In hospitals, nursing services have a very strategic position in determining the quality of service (4).

A nurse is someone who has graduated from higher education in Nursing, both in and out of the country that is recognized by the Government in accordance with the provisions of Laws and Regulations (Law of the Republic of Indonesia 2014). *The World Health Organization (WHO)* in 2020 stated that the global nursing workforce was 27.9 million people, while in Indonesia, according to data from the Central Statistics Agency in 2022, the number of nursing workers was 563,739 people. Data from the Central Statistics Agency of Southeast Sulawesi and Kendari City was obtained by 9,172 people and in Kendari City as many as 1,245 people. In addition to handling patients, nursing staff also have other jobs including pushing oxygen cylinders, carrying medical equipment, treating patients' wounds, bathing patients, and writing patient data, lifting patients.

A high proportion of nurses must be in line with nurses who are competent or have good performance. This means that the high proportion of nurses must be balanced with the quality that the nurse has in providing services. If the proportion of nurses is high but their competence is low, then the quality of health services can decrease, which ultimately has an impact on patient safety and satisfaction. Because good performance is reflected in the nursing care provided to patients. Good nurse performance is a determining factor in the image of hospitals in the community and supports in achieving organizational goals (5). Nursing as a profession and nurses as professionals who have the responsibility to provide nursing services in accordance with their competence and authority independently or in collaboration with other members of the health sector. The performance of nurses in providing nursing services must be based on high abilities so that they can support the implementation of nurses' duties in providing quality nursing care (6).

One of the methods in assessing nurse performance is to look at nursing care standards. Nurses as professionals must be able to provide nursing care to patients as described in the implementation of the action plan determined with the intention of meeting the needs of patients to the maximum. Nurse performance can be measured by how well nurses perform their duties in accordance with applicable nursing care standards. This includes the fulfillment of duties, the accuracy of procedures, as well as the effectiveness in providing safe and quality care. Nursing care standards are guidelines that nurses must follow when providing services to patients. Nurse performance assessments are conducted by looking at whether they are following these standard procedures correctly, including steps in conducting

examinations, interventions, monitoring, and documentation. Nurses who carry out their duties according to standards are considered to have good performance (7).

A high workload of nurses can cause a decrease in nurse performance and lack or poor communication between patients and nurses, affecting the patient's condition, thus having an impact on the poor quality of nursing services (8). If nurses have a high workload, it can have a great influence on the provision of nursing care provided to patients and their families, so that the level of patient satisfaction with the provision of nursing care may decrease (9).

Motivation is an activity that puts a person or a group who has certain and personal needs, to work to complete their tasks. Motivation is a strength, encouragement, need, pressure and psychological mechanism that is intended to be an accumulation of internal factors (a person who has the values of hard work) and external will be more motivated to work hard if their work environment is supportive) (10)

One form of appreciation is that hospitals must provide rewards for services that have been issued by workers at the agency. Providing incentives will affect employee behavior in their work, so the hospital needs to pay attention to the logical consequences for employees to improve work performance. Incentives are a form of reward or reward to employees in the form of money that is irregular or at any time based on performance and achievements that have been achieved with the aim of increasing employee motivation and work productivity (11)

Kindergarten IV dr. Ismoyo Kendari Hospital and Bhayangkara Hospital are type C hospitals. Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. HK. 03.05/I/2026/1102.04.3.2.4548 concerning the determination of the class of the Indonesian Army National Army Hospital (TNI-AD) Level IV 14.07.03 Dr. R. Ismoyo Kendari. Bhayangkara Kendari Hospital Receives a Certificate of Hospital Class Determination Designated as a Class C General Hospital from the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number: HK.02.03/I/0436/2015 dated February 26, 2015.

The initial data survey was carried out by researchers on November 5, 2024, namely interviewing 7 implementing nurses at the Kindergarten IV Hospital dr. Ismoyo Kendari. Class 1,2,3 inpatient rooms consist of 30 patient beds, VIP inpatient rooms consist of 13 patient beds, isolation rooms consist of 6 beds and ICU inpatient rooms consist of 10 patient beds. The staff in this room work in three shifts, namely morning, afternoon and night, in each shift consists of 2-3 implementing nurses. Meanwhile, at Bhayangkara Hospital, the inpatient rooms of classes 1, 2, and 3 consist of 55 patient beds, the VIP inpatient room consists of 19 patient beds, the isolation room consists of 12 beds and the ICU inpatient room consists of 6 patient beds. The staff in this room works in three shifts, namely morning, afternoon and night, each shift consists of 3-4 implementing nurses.

The results of interviews with nurses and inpatient managers regarding the performance of nurses in the inpatient rooms of dr. Ismoyo Kendari Kindergarten IV Hospital and Bhayangkara Hospital, that in terms of quality, nurses are quite responsive in identifying patient complaints, but are often slow in handling these complaints, and sometimes the excuse is to wait for confirmation from other medical teams regarding patient complaints. In the aspect of quantity, which is how much work a nurse achieves according to her main duties and functions, in this case there are still some nurses in the inpatient room who have not been able to meet the nursing care target according to the SOP, and it often happens that nurses do not participate when visiting the patient's room during the operation because they feel that the record of the shift and CPPT (Integrated Patient Development Record) in the medical record has represented the explanation of the patient's condition. This CPPT serves as a comprehensive record of the development of a patient's condition during treatment. In the aspect of punctuality, which is the ability to complete at a predetermined time and maximize the time available for other activities, in this case, there are still nurses who go home before the schedule of the shift pass, but there are also nurses who go home late because the work has not been completed/delayed. In terms of effectiveness, nurses in the inpatient rooms of dr. Ismoyo Kendari Kindergarten IV Hospital and Bhayangkara Hospital are generally skilled in carrying out their duties in accordance with their positions and functions, but there are nurses who are not able to make maximum use of the facilities in the room such as nurses in carrying out actions to patients not carrying trolleys, combs or plastic garbage bags, and do not pay attention to the principles of cleanliness and sterility in nursing procedures on patients.

The phenomenon of low performance of nurses in the provision of nursing services based on problems in the research site and strengthened by relevant research findings and the existence of a *research gap* with previous research that only examined nursing care and documentation, the researcher was interested in conducting research on the description of nurses' performance in the provision of nursing services in the Inpatient Room of Kindergarten IV dr. Ismoyo Kendari Hospital and the Hospital Bhayangkara. Based on the background description above, this is the basis for the researcher to conduct a study entitled "Analysis of Factors Affecting Nurse Performance in Type C Hospital Inpatient Rooms in 2024".

2. Method

This type of research uses analytical research that is observational. This study uses a *cross-sectional* research design with univariate test, bivariate test and multivariate test to analyze factors that affect the performance of nurses in the Type C Hospital Inpatient Room in 2024. This approach is used to look at each other with other variables.

3. Results

3.1. The effect between workload on Nurse Performance

Table 1 Distribution of the Effect of Workload on Nurse Performance in Type C Hospital Inpatient Rooms in 2024

Workload	Nurse Performance				Sum		ρ Value
	Good		Less		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Heavy	32	64.0	18	36.0	50	100	0.001
Light	21	25.9	60	74.1	81	100	
Total	53	40.5	78	59.5	131	100	

Source: Data Primer December 2024

Table 1 shows that the proportion of respondents who have a heavy workload with good nurse performance is 32 respondents (64.0%) and poor performance is 18 respondents (36.0%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who have a light workload with good nurse performance is 21 respondents (25.9%) and poor performance is 60 respondents (74.1%). Based on the results of the statistical test with *chi-square* on the workload variable, a value $\rho = 0.001$ was obtained, where the value ρ of $< \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is an effect of workload on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital in 2024

3.2. The Effect of Service Period on Nurse Performance

Table 2 Distribution of the Influence of Working Period on Nurses' Performance in Type C Hospital Inpatient Rooms in 2024

Working Period	Nurse Performance				Sum		ρ Value
	Good		Less		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
New	22	37.3	37	62.7	59	100	0.312
Old	31	43.1	41	56.9	72	100	
Total	53	40.5	78	59.5	131	100	

Source: Data Primer December 2024

Table 2 shows that the proportion of respondents who have a new working period with good nurse performance is 22 respondents (37.3%) and poor performance is 37 respondents (62.7%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had a long working period with good nurse performance was 31 respondents (43.1%) and poor performance was 41 respondents (56.9%). Based on the results of the statistical test with *chi-square* on the variable of service period, a value of $p = 0.312$ was obtained, where the value of $p > \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is no effect on the working period, there is a performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital in 2024.

3.3. The Effect of Motivation on Nurse Performance

Table 3 Distribution of the Influence of Motivation on Nurse Performance in Type C Hospital Inpatient Rooms in 2024

Motivation	Nurse Performance				Sum		ρ Value
	Good		Less		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Good	42	87.5	6	12.5	48	100	0.001
Less	11	13.3	72	86.7	83	100	
Total	53	40.5	78	59.5	131	100	

Source: Data Primer December 2024

Table 3 shows that the proportion of respondents who have good motivation with good nurse performance is 42 respondents (87.5%) and poor performance is 6 respondents (12.5%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had less motivation with good nurse performance was 11 respondents (13.3%) and poor performance was 72 respondents (86.7%). Based on the results of the statistical test with *chi-square* on the motivation variable, a value of $p = 0.001$ was obtained, where the value of $p < \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is an influence of motivation on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital in 2024.

3.4. The Effect of Incentives on Nurse Performance

Table 4 Distribution of the Effect of Incentives on Nurse Performance in Type C Hospital Inpatient Rooms in 2024

Incentive	Nurse Performance				Sum		ρ Value
	Good		Less		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Enough	35	66.0	18	34.0	53	100	0.001
Less	18	23.1	60	76.9	78	100	
Total	53	40.5	78	59.5	131	100	

Source: Data Primer December 2024

Table 4 shows that the proportion of respondents who have sufficient incentives with good nurse performance is 35 respondents (66.0%) and poor performance is 18 respondents (34.0%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who have less incentives with good nurse performance is 18 respondents (23.1%) and poor performance is 60 respondents (76.9%). Based on the results of the statistical test with *chi-square* on the incentive variable, a value of $p = 0.001$ was obtained, where the value of $p < \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is an influence of incentives on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital in 2024.

3.5. Multivariate Analysis

Table 5 Results of the Logistics Regression R Test on Variables Affecting Nurse Performance

Sub Variabel	Wald	Sig	Exp (B)
Beban Kerja	3.235	0.072	2.661
Masa Kerja	0.004	0.949	0.966
Motivasi	28.593	<0.001	42.991
Insentif	0.156	0.693	0.758

Source: Data Primer December 2024

Table 5 in the table of *variables in the equation* above using logistic regression analysis, there are several variables that affect nurse performance, namely workload variables, work periods, motivation, and incentives. While the variable that

has the most influence on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital is the Motivation variable with a significance value (sig) of $<.001$, $p < \alpha$ (0.25) and the *odd ratio* (OR) = 42.991 is the largest value among other variables

4. Discussion

4.1. The effect between workload on Nurse Performance

This is because nurses feel they need additional time to be able to complete the work. In this case, it means that nurses understand their duties and the working time they have. Patient visitation is carried out by several nurses every 3 times a day where they every day have to meet with patients who have a different history of diseases so that no matter how many patients are handled every day and the tasks are undertaken, nurses are always ready and work optimally by taking advantage of the available time. The lack of nurses is one of the workload of nurses because the number of each patient is always increasing, but in work, nurses are always fully responsible for carrying out patient care until they are cured by giving intensive medicines.

The factors that affect a person's workload can be classified into internal factors and external factors. Internal factors such as the condition of the nurse itself means the high ability and hard work of the nurse in carrying out her duties and responsibilities. Meanwhile, external factors are the imbalance in the number of nurses and the number of patients, an uncomfortable physical environment, poor inter-relationship relationships, demands from hospitals that require nurses to always provide quality nursing care services (12)

4.2. The Effect of Motivation on Nurse Performance

The working life of nurses is often considered one of the factors that affect their performance in hospital inpatient rooms. However, the results of this study showed that there was no significant relationship between the working period and the performance of nurses. This is interesting to analyze further, considering the many assumptions circulating in the community that the longer a nurse's working life, the better her performance. Nurse performance is influenced by various factors, including training, motivation, and work environment, which may be more relevant compared to the tenure itself (13).

By considering the various factors that have been discussed, it can be concluded that tenure is not the only indicator of nurse performance. This study emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach in evaluating nurse performance, where education, training, work environment, and individual motivation should be the main focus. Therefore, hospitals need to develop programs that support the professional development of nurses on an ongoing basis to improve their performance in the inpatient setting.

4.3. The Effect of Motivation on Nurse Performance

Based on the description above, according to the researcher, work motivation is an important factor for nurses to carry out the duties that are the responsibility of nurses, without work motivation, work will not be able to run well. If the work motivation of nurses is high, then nurses can work optimally so that they can produce good performance as well. The low performance of individual work is caused by low abilities and skills, lack of motivation, weak instruction and lack of support for organizational implementation services. Respondents whose work motivation is not good and have poor performance due to the lack of work motivation in nurses will ultimately result in a decrease in work results (performance) produced by nurses. Meanwhile, respondents who have poor work motivation but their performance is likely due to a comfortable work environment and good support from colleagues, so that the performance they produce has also increased. Respondents who have good work motivation and poor performance are clearly a supporting factor for good performance, because the higher the work motivation of nurses, the higher the performance will be. Respondents with good work motivation who have good performance may be due to a lack of supervision by the head nurse and a lack of support from colleagues.

4.4. The Effect of Incentives on Nurse Performance

This is because the provision of incentives to nurses is given in accordance with the provisions of the hospital which is given in the form of money every month. Incentives given to health workers, especially nurses who carry out their duties in accordance with what is expected. However, the amount of incentives received by each health worker, especially nurses, is not known because the receipt of incentives is also related to employee performance targets (SKP) which are confidential so that it is not possible to compare the provision of incentives between one hospital and another. We know

that providing incentives can increase the work spirit of health workers, especially nurses, and can also be an additional income to meet their daily needs.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion on the Analysis of Factors Affecting Nurse Performance in the Inpatient Room of Type C Hospital in 2024, it can be concluded as follows: There is an influence of workload, motivation and incentives on the performance of nurses in the inpatient room of type C hospitals in 2024 and there was no effect on the performance of nurses in the Type C Hospital Inpatient Room in 2024

Suggestion

On behalf of the hospital, It is necessary to make a policy related to the career development of nurses based on competence and performance so that they remain motivated in working even with a high workload.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

If studies involve use of animal/human subject, authors must give appropriate statement of ethical approval. If not applicable then mention 'The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors'.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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